

Viscosity Behaviour of *o*-Amino Benzoic Acid and *o*-Amino Benzoate Ion in Aqueous Solution

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Relative viscosities of aqueous solutions of *o*-aminobenzoic acid and its Li-, Na- and K- salts have been measured in the temperature range 25-35°. The Jones-Dole viscosity B-coefficients of the *o*-aminobenzoate ion and its salts increase with increasing temperature indicating a structure breaking effect. The B-value of *o*-aminobenzoic acid, however, decreases with rise in temperature suggesting that *o*-aminobenzoic acid is a structure maker. The larger B-value of the *o*-aminobenzoate ion compared to that of *o*-aminobenzoic acid molecule confirms similar behaviour observed in the acetate ion and acetic acid and benzoate ion and benzoic acid systems.

THE studies on the viscosity B-coefficients of aqueous solutions of acetic acid and alkali metal acetates by various workers^{1,2} show that the B-coefficient of acetate ion ($B=0.25$) is much larger than that of the acetic acid molecule ($B=0.12$). It has been suggested^{3,4} that this is due to an enhanced order producing nature of the acetate ion and not to any effect of size since the molecule acetic acid is almost of identical size with the acetate ion. Similar behaviour has been observed in aqueous solution for benzoic acid molecule and benzoate ion⁵. In the present communication we report the results of viscosity measurements on aqueous solutions of *o*-aminobenzoic acid and its Li-, Na- and K-salts in the temperature range 25-35°. The purpose of undertaking the present investigation is to examine whether the introduction of a substituent in the *o*-position of benzoic acid molecule influences or not the solvent structure and consequently the solute-solvent interaction of the resulting acid and the anion of the acid. As an ortho-substituent we have chosen in the present investigation the amino group which is known to interact with the carboxylic acid function and the carboxylate ion through H-bond formation and hence is expected to influence the hydrodynamical behaviour of the solution through solvent structure modification.

Experimental

Pure *o*-aminobenzoic acid (E. Merck., A.R.) after repeated recrystallisation was used for the preparation of alkalimetal salts of the acid. Equivalent amounts of *o*-aminobenzoic acid and A.R. grade alkalimetal carbonates were mixed in a minimum volume of water to obtain a clear solution from which the salt was slowly crystallized. The repeatedly crystallized salt was finally washed several times with distilled ether and dried. Stock solutions of alkali metal *o*-aminobenzoates were prepared from

the dried salts by direct weighing. Solutions of varying concentrations were then prepared from the stock solutions by dilution. Densities of solutions were measured by a calibrated weld-type pycnometer of about 40 ml capacity provided with a graduated stem fitted with a standard joint stopper at its upper end. All viscosity measurements were made in a specially designed high flow time Ostwald viscometer which was placed in a thermostat regulated within $\pm 0.005^\circ$. The measured flow times were reproducible within ± 0.2 seconds. For the calibration of the viscometer the observed flow times of freshly prepared triple distilled water at two different temperatures, viz. 30° and 35° are 867.8" and 785.5" seconds respectively. The viscometer constants A' and B' were determined according to

$$\frac{\eta}{d} = A't - B't \quad (1)$$

where η (CP) is the viscosity, d is the density (g.ml^{-3}) and t is the flow time in seconds. The viscometer constants A' and B' were found to be $9.299 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and 5.21109 respectively.

Results and Discussion

The experimental results of the relative viscosities of the aqueous solutions of orthoaminobenzoates and orthoaminobenzoic acid have been analysed by the Jones-Dole equation⁶ (2).

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where $\frac{\eta}{\eta_0}$ is the relative viscosity, C is the molar concentration, and A and B are constants characteristic of the electrolyte. The results of the A and B

TABLE 1

Salt and free acid	B _{salt}			B-			ΔE [‡] 25°C cals	A _{salt}		
	25°C	30°C	35°C	25°C	30°C	35°C		25°C	30°C	35°C
Li- <i>o</i> -aminobenzoate	0.500	0.514	0.519	0.95	0.97	0.98	-451	0.01	0.000	0.008
Na- <i>o</i> -aminobenzoate	0.391	0.414	0.427	0.90	0.93	0.94	-540	0.017	0.010	0.0025
K- <i>o</i> -aminobenzoate	0.310	0.339	0.353	0.92	0.92	0.95	-607	0.014	0.004	0.000
<i>o</i> -aminobenzoic acid	0.280	0.270	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Standard deviations in B_{salt} values over 25–35°C are ±0.012–.022 for Li-salt, ±0.008–.017 for Na-salt, and ±0.012–.045 for K-salt respectively. Standard deviations in A-coefficient for the corresponding salts over the same temperature range are ±.002–.004, ±.001–.002 and ±.002–.004 respectively.

coefficients of all the solutes studied are recorded in Table 1.

The theoretical values of the viscosity A-coefficient at 25° calculated by the Falkenhagen-Vernon⁷ equation are found to be 0.0095, 0.0082, 0.0068 and 0.003 for lithium, sodium and potassium salts and ortho-aminobenzoic acid respectively. A comparison of these results with the respective values observed experimentally (cf. column A salt at 25° of Table 1) shows a fair agreement, although at higher temperatures low values of A-coefficients have been observed in some cases. Very low and even negative A-values have been observed by many workers, e.g., by Kay *et al.*⁸ in some aqueous tetraalkylammonium salt solutions, by Yao and Benion⁹ in their studies on the viscosity of electrolytes in dimethyl sulphoxide, by Blokhra *et al.*¹⁰ in the study of viscosity of electrolytes in mixed solvents. The standard deviations in the values of A- and B-coefficients show that errors in the B-values are smaller than those in A.

From the column 2 of the Table 1 it is seen that for each salt studied B-salt increases with temperature, suggesting that the salts are behaving as structure breakers. B values calculated by using the conventional splitting procedure¹¹ are listed in the column 3 of the Table 1. From an inspection of the data in the said column it will not be prudent to assign any unique value to the ionic viscosity B-coefficient of the orthoaminobenzoate ion at any particular temperature since B values depend on the nature of the cation partner.

This observation of cation sensitiveness of the B value of *o*-aminobenzoate ion indicates that the resultant structure of aqueous solutions of alkali metal anthranilates are built up co-operatively by both the cation and anion.

Further B values show an increase with rise in temperature. This is clearly noticeable in the case of Li- and Na- salts but not so with the K- salt except at the higher temperatures. Since the B values show no regular variation from Na to K, we have, following Nightingale Jr. and Benck¹², calculated the energy of activation for viscous flow (ΔE[‡]) for the said anion at 25° and ΔE[‡] values are found to be -451, -540 and -607 cal for lithium,

sodium and potassium salts respectively. This decreasing order of the ΔE[‡] values from Li to K establishes the cation sensitive structural modification of the water structure by the anion. This behaviour is expected on the basis of the 'localised hydrolysis'¹³ model of ion-solvent interaction since *o*-aminobenzoic acid is a weak acid. On the basis of this model the B values at any particular temperature should decrease systematically from Li to K. While this expectation is fulfilled by lithium and sodium salts, in the case of K- salt a slight increase in the B value compared to that of the sodium salt is observed on the contrary. The reason for this is obscure at present. This unusual behaviour of the potassium salt cannot be ascribed to any sort of experimental error since the experiment has been repeated several times and each time the same result has been observed. Moreover, we have observed identical behaviour of the potassium salts in some other systems related to substituted benzoate salts (unpublished work).

From the Table it is seen that the B-coefficient for the *o*-aminobenzoate ion is greater than that for the anthranilic acid molecule. The larger values of the B-coefficients for the *o*-aminobenzoate ion than that for the *o*-aminobenzoic acid molecule confirm similar behaviour observed in the acetic acid-acetate ion and benzoic acid-benzoate ion cases. The B-coefficient of *o*-aminobenzoic acid molecule, however, decreases with rise in temperature suggesting that the free acid molecule is a structure maker in the temperature range studied.

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